

QUIZ**LAST NAME:** Idigo**FIRST NAME:** Joseph**PROGRAM CODE:** LLM**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 2010, window 8

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. ‘When writing papers one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism.’ Which is the best way to cite this quotation?**
 - ‘When writing papers (EUCLID 2015, 8) one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism.’
 - ‘When writing papers one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism. (EUCLID, 2015, 8).’
 - ‘When writing papers one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 8)’.
 - ‘When writing papers one of the most important things the writer should do is avoid Plagiarism’ (EUCLID 2015, 8).¹**
- 2. A writer reproduces the passage in Question 1 above as: It is always important not to succumb to plagiarism when you write. What has this writer done?**

¹ EUCLID, 'ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1 Essay Writing,' *Euclid University*, 2015, 8

- The writer has paraphrased the passage.
- The writer has created an idea from the passage.
- The writer has not paraphrased the passage.²**
- Having created an idea, the writer need not cite it.

3. **Why is 'writing portfolio' important?**

- It carries your writing in one secure bag.
- It helps to give a fair assessment of a writer.³**
- All of the above.
- None of the above.

4. **What is the best layout for this statement, using the UK punctuation?**

- Reynold says, 'Today's students will go through an average of four careers in one life span.'⁴**
- Reynolds says; 'Today's students will go through an average of four careers in one life span'.
- Reynolds says: 'Today's students will go through an average of four careers in one life span.'
- Reynolds says, 'Today's students will go through an average of four careers in one life span'.

² Ibid.

³ Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 41.

⁴ Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer, 413.

5. **Which statement below best reflects research procedures?**
- You think up hard reasons as you collect hard evidence.
 - Reasons need support of evidence, but evidence needs reference to a reliable source.⁵**
 - A reason is abstract and must be cited as you cite the sources of evidence.
 - All the above are correct.
6. **Which of these is the most correct statement about bibliography?**
- You list sources at the end of the paper in a bibliography.
 - Sources in a note are not cited in a bibliography.
 - The list in a bibliography contains sources cited in a note plus sources not cited earlier.⁶**
 - None of the above is correct in a bibliography.
7. **Which of these is an error in a technical paper?**
- Use of direct quotes to illustrate a point.⁷**
 - Use of the present tense of a verb to describe facts in public domain.
 - Has not defined terms already known to an audience.
 - Has not made reference to his instructors and other teams.

⁵ Turabian, 38.

⁶ Turabian, 91.

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4* (EUCLID, 2015), 5-8.

8. **Which is correct among the following?**
- 'Plagiarism is defined as presenting someone else's work as your own.' (EUCLID 2015, 77).
 - 'Plagiarism is defined as presenting someone else's work as your own' (EUCLID 2015, p.77).⁸**
 - 'Plagiarism is defined as presenting someone else's work as your own (EUCLID 2015, p.77).'
 - 'Plagiarism is defined as presenting someone else's work as your own. (EUCLID 2015, p.77)'.
9. **What is the most accurate description of the 'Bluepages' in the *Bluebook*?**
- The names, 'Bluepages' and the *Bluebook* are interchangeable.
 - The 'Bluepages' are used in academic legal documents.
 - The 'Bluepages' direct readers to other parts of the *Bluebook* for answers to some questions.⁹**
 - Only seasoned practitioners use the 'Bluepages'.
10. **Which of these statements best describe the contents of the 'Whitepages'?**
- The contents advertise the works of the publishers.
 - The contents supply rules not seen in the 'Bluepages' and local courts.¹⁰**

⁸ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4* (EUCLID, 2015), 77.

⁹ *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation, Nineteenth Edition*. Edited by Prince, Mary. Massachusetts: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2013., 24-25.

¹⁰ Ibid.

- The contents are listings of laws outside the United States.
- The contents provide easy navigation through the entire book.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1 Essay Writing*. Euclid University, 2015. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf>. (accessed 3 January 2020).

EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4*. EUCLID, 2015. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/YIJXVLgPv0/> (accessed 3 January 2020).

Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. Wilmington, Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation, Nineteenth Edition. Edited by Prince, Mary. Massachusetts: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2013.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers, Eighth Edition*. Revised by Booth, Wayne, Gregory Colomb and Joseph Williams. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.